

1 **Kinase and phosphatase inhibition as a signal transduction-centric approach to adjunctive**
2 **chemotherapies for the treatment of gynecologic cancers: PTPRJ.**

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7 Men and women differ in large part resulting from the presence or absence of gynecologic organs
8 including the ovaries, the uterus, the lining of which is known as the endometrium, and the entry to the
9 uterus (womb), the cervix (1), all of which are targets for development of malignancies (2-7); vulvar
10 cancer is less common (8). Cancer, or unrestricted cell division which develops into a tumor after
11 remaining unchecked, evades active cell death and cell cycle control mechanisms, sustaining its survival
12 through growth factor signals (9) which are transduced to the nucleus to activate and repress transcription
13 of genes (10, 11). These signals are transduced between the plasma membrane and the nucleus by the
14 action of kinases and phosphatases, enzymes that utilize conformational changes and a catalytic site to
15 translate a signal from the extracellular environment to a change in gene expression. Catalytic sites are
16 pharmacologically targetable, and small molecule targeting of the appropriate kinase or phosphatase target
17 will disrupt or block this transduction (12, 13). We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (14, 15) to
18 identify and validate kinase and phosphatase targets in gynecologic oncology, including cancer of the
19 ovary, or epithelial ovarian cancer. Here we describe a differentially expressed, up-regulated, and
20 catalytically available phosphatase target in epithelial ovarian cancer: PTPRJ.

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26 **Keywords:** kinase, phosphatase, signal transduction, gynecologic oncology, therapeutic targets in cancer,
27 chemical biology, systems biology of human cancer.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), the proteome (total collection of proteins in the cell) and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of human cancer (16-20). This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - cancer subtypes, like adeno and squamous forms of non-small cell lung cancer, metastasis to distant sites, including the lymph nodes, the lungs, the liver, the brain, and bones, and the circulating tumor stem cell, which emerges from the primary tumor, disseminates through the body and establishes a novel entity in a separate organ (21-26).

Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), administered in combination with FDA approved broad-spectrum chemotherapeutics like CDK4/6 inhibitors, and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies (27, 28) to blindly identify disease-specific, subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities, fully augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe a phosphatase therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the ovarian tumor transcriptome - a phosphatase target that is up-regulated and catalytically available: PTPRJ.

Results

Figure 1: PTPRJ is differentially expressed in ovarian cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the ovary from humans with epithelial ovarian cancer.

n=3 normal ovarian tissue

n=8 primary tumors (ovary; human)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_24_P921321	5.17E-03	-3.4250444	-2.30172	-1.82522423	PTPRJ	3113/40462	92.3

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the normal ovarian tissue and in primary tumors of humans with epithelial ovarian cancer (14), we discovered differential expression of protein tyrosine phosphatase, receptor type J, encoded by *PTPRJ* in epithelial ovarian cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of PTPRJ changed more than 90% of the human ovarian tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 40,462 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PTPRJ messenger RNA in ovarian tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of PTPRJ during transformation of the ovary.

II. Primary tumors of the ovary from humans with ovarian cancer.

n=3 normal ovarian tissue

n=40 primary tumors (ovary; human)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7939839	1.42E-05	-4.8771088	2.9525065	-1.6617423	PTPRJ	598/29088	97.9

1 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with
2 epithelial ovarian cancer relative to normal ovarian tissue, in a second microarray dataset (15) from
3 independent investigators, we validated differential expression of PTPRJ in epithelial ovarian cancer in
4 humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of PTPRJ here changed more than 95% of the human ovarian tumor
5 transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 29,088
6 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PTPRJ messenger
7 RNA in ovarian tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of PTPRJ during transformation of the ovary.

8 Thus, differential and increased expression of PTPRJ defines the transcriptional landscape of
9 epithelial ovarian cancer in humans.

10 **Discussion**

11 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
12 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy). Small
13 molecule inhibitors of PTPRJ phosphatase, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be
14 tested for efficacy in patients with epithelial ovarian cancer, with the goal of identifying the most effective
15 phosphatase inhibitors for management of gynecologic malignancies. An approach that combines kinase
16 and phosphatase targeting with a recently described multi-catalytic strategy that targets dNTP synthesis,
17 replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, likely delivered in conjunction
18 with standard chemotherapies and drug resistance pump inhibitors in resistant cases, is most likely to be
19 most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance and disease (29).
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Methods

We utilized GSE124766 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in primary tumors from humans with ovarian cancer, as compared to normal ovarian (along with GSE146556 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).